

A Kansei Study of the Sounds of Different Bottom Area of Heeled Shoes

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the sound of heeled shoes. First, the paper will point out the importance of sound in the design field. Even though sound design is a key point of product design, few paper have studied it. In our daily lives, most of the products make sounds. This research looks at the sounds of heeled shoes. We will use SD method to do the experiment. In the end we hope to know what people feel about the different sounds, the difference between male and female perceptions, and the effect of different materials on the sense of the sound.

Key words: *sound, heeled shoes, kansei*

1. Introduction

Because economic develop quickly these days, there are many kinds and brands of products. For that matter, people have more choice in their favorite products. So how companies attract people to buy their products is becoming an important issue. Some studies point out that product images play an important role when people make their decisions [1, 2]. For most of the consumers, the product is not just a product but one of their symbolic objects which can show their personal characteristics and their status [3]. According to these, we know that designing the product image is a key point to improve the features and increasing sale volume of a product.

It is well known that human are sensory animals with five senses: tactile sense, olfactory sense, auditory sense, gustatory sense, and visual sense. People can use these senses to explore and experience this world. During the last few decades, people are only concerned with the functions or appearances of the products; consumers only use their visual sense to make decisions. Many papers have studied the elements of appearance. However, some designers point out that if five senses can work together, it will provide better experiences to users. By designing the multiple sensory of a product, it will enrich user experience, deepen the product's impression, and satisfy the consumers' desire. Therefore, we should not only design the appearances or functions of a product, but also its texture, smell, sound, and taste if possible.

Among the five senses, however, most of the products do not provide smell or taste. In addition, most of us can associate the product texture with its looks. In other words, most of the product designs have already combined tactile sense and visual sense together. Therefore we are more interested in studying the auditory sense. For

example, what is our expectation when a product makes pleasing sounds and attracts us to buy it? There are many studies focusing on the product sound design. They want to find out that what role auditory sense plays and how consumers will respond to the products [4-7]. If we can take sound design into consideration or use it effectively, it will bring more sensory stimulations to the consumers [8]. Besides, designing sounds often indicates sophistication in the engineering of the product, and also increases the perceived value of the product [9].

That is, a well-designed sound will enhance the product experience. On the other hand, unsatisfactory auditory experience will bring a negative influence to product's value. Therefore, in the last decade, more studies have paid attentions to improve the quality of product sounds and consequently the product experience [6, 9-14].

Although the sound might be one of important elements of product design, very few companies and studies take it into their consideration [3, 8]. In addition, within the field of product development, the designers are not very clear about sound design yet. However, it's still important for a designer to be aware of what kind of the sense consumers will have when they listen to different sounds. This kind of knowledge can help designers to design a product which can leave people with a stronger impression when they use it.

Most of the senses, including the sound, can be summarized on a semantic level or an emotional level [4, 14, 15]. This paper will focus on the sounds of heeled shoes. It will try to find the relationship between Kansei words and the sounds. Why have we chosen the heeled-shoes to be the study object? The reason is that for many women, heeled-shoes are one of the bare necessities of life. They like to wear this kind of shoes. On the other hand, people hear the shoe sounds frequently every day. Sometimes we will look forward to see a woman by the sounds we hear. So, how do most women choose their shoes? Most of them pick out shoes by what kind of impression they want to make on other people, such as sexy, cute, fashionable, and so on. So we want know what consumers will feel about the shoe sounds. With discovering the factors of auditory sensation and combine it with the looks of the product, it will make a stronger impression on people. It would help the designers to use this kind of knowledge to design for consumer demands and satisfaction

Shoes can be decomposed into many parts (Figure 1). There are too many elements that we cannot take all of these into consider in this experiment. Although these factors, such as heel thickness and curvature, will all affect the walking sound, experts say that the bottom area of a shoe is the main factor that determines the sound. In this case we only pick out the bottom area to be the independent variable.

This study uses the method of semantic difference and compares the significant differences to analyze the test data. Thus, we can find out what kind of feeling people have when they hear the sounds. Also we are interested in learning if the feelings would be different with different genders? How about walking on different material of the floors? Will the heel materials affect the sounds or feelings?

Figure.1 The structure of a shoe.

2. Method

This experiment uses the method of semantic difference to do the questionnaire. According to this method we can construct the relationship principle between the sounds and the heeled shoes' product image.

Figure.2 The framework.

This experiment can be separated into five parts (Figure 2, step 2~step 6). First step is collecting the Kansei adjectives and grouping them to be the bipolar Kansei words. Second, we pick out the shoes and record the sounds to be the experiment's samples, and then use the method of semantic difference to make the questionnaire and run a pilot study. Last, according to the result of the pilot study, we modify the experiment's processes, and do the regular test. The following will describe the details of the experiment processes.

2.1. Kansei adjectives

The adjectives used in the questionnaire must be able to describe the shoes' sounds and its product image. For that matter we surfed some shoes' websites and magazines to gather the adjectives which are frequently used to describe the shoes. Finally there are 23 adjectives listed as following: casual, sweet, cute, retro, temperament, charming, loveable, simple, natural, elegant, low-profile, sumptuous, young, has personality, unrestrained, sexy, classic, noble, street fashion, handsome, military, and gentle.

However, there are too many adjectives and some of them are similar. So we asked five design students to use KJ method to group these adjectives, and told them each adjective group must have a representative adjective and a negative adjective. Then, these adjectives were categorized into six pairs of the bipolar Kansei words: retro—modern, formal—casual, vulgar—temperament, young—old, flighty—steady, and noble—poor. Finally, take these six pairs of adjectives to make the semantic difference questionnaire.

2.2. Shoes' walking sounds

There are many factors which will affect the shoes' sounds, such as: the heel's material, the height, the bottom area, the material of the floor, and the person wearing it. Thus, the experiment must define clearly the independent variable and dependent variables. Three variables will be discussed in the following sections.

2.2.1 Shoes

We start the discussion from the shoes. There are some elements of the shoes' heel. For example: height, bottom area, form, material, bottom shape and so on. After asking shoe store clerks for advice, they pointed out that thin or thick heels will make the most obvious difference in sounds. In other words, the sound will differ from each other by different heel bottom areas. Therefore, in this case we choose the bottom area to be the independent variable. There are three sample shoes, all of them are 7cm in height and the heel's material all are plastic. (Figure 3)

Figure.3 The sample shoes (the black shape is shoes' bottom area).

(a) $2r=1.2\text{cm}$ (b) $1.2*2.2\text{cm}$ (c) $2*2\text{cm}$

2.2.2 Floor

Walking on different material floors will also make different sounds. So we would like to know if people still feel the same with the same shoes walking on floors with different materials. Although asphalt road is the road that we most frequently walk on, the environment is usually too noisy to hear the shoes sound. That is why we have chosen wooden floor and tiles, which are often used in the interior environment (Figure 4).

Figure.4 The floor samples (wood & tile).

2.2.3 People

Walking posture will also affect the sounds. To minimize the differences, this study asks the same person to wear these three sample shoes and walk with the same cadence and force. At the same time, the sounds are recorded by a recorder.

2.3. Pilot study

We have a pilot study before the regular experiment to make sure things are modified for the experiment. This pilot study uses six pairs of the bipolar Kansei words to make the 7 scales Likert-type questionnaire. Each sample has ten footsteps and the lengths of the samples are all 7 seconds. Additionally, there is a 6-second blank between each sample. The experiment uses the same computer to broadcast the sounds (Figure 5). To avoid the environmental interference, we ask participants to wear the same earphone to do the test.

Figure.5 The sound samples.

2.4. Experiment

We have two participants for the pilot study. After the pilot study, we have an interview with them. Both of them said that auditory is not as sensitive as visual, so seven scales are too many. In addition, they all ask for more footsteps for each sound sample to do the questionnaire. They advise to repeat the sounds until participants finish marking the scales, then change to the next sample.

So the regular experiment has been modified to use 5 scales Likert-type questionnaire. Each sound will be repeated until participants scale the grade, then change to the next sound. The experiment will use the same computer to broadcast the sound. To avoid the environmental interference, we will ask participants to wear the same earphone to do the test.

2.5. Results

This experiment has 24 participants in total. There are 11 males and 13 females. Most of them are 20-25 years old. The analysis starts from the gender differences (Table 1). We can know that in most conditions males and females feel the same (31/36 conditions are the same), but they still have some differences between their answers. The average scores of the 5 scales Likert-type questionnaire are shown in Table 2. The higher score means the feeling is closer to the upper adjectives in the pair. Then the comparison data of three pairs of shoes and the two materials of the floors are listed in Table 2, 3, and 4. The outcome, in table 3, shows that most shoes have significant different sounds between different material floors. Table 4 points out that when the shoes are walking on the wooden floor, people cannot tell the differences between three pairs of the shoes.

Then the test uses Duncan to group the grades. Just as the outcome of table 4, when the independent variable is the material of the floor, that Duncan can't group the results to be different groups. When the independent variables are shoes' bottom area it has the same problem in some cases. So this paper only shows the results

which can be grouped in table 5 and table 6. Table 5 points out that the smaller the heel bottom area, the more modern and younger the feel is. Also, from table 6, we can know that (1.2*2.2)*tile and (2r=1.2)*tile are more modern, younger than the others. Temperature and vulgar are closer related to the material of the floor. Participants feel that (1.2*2.2)*tile is more casual than (2r=1.2)*wooden and (2*2)*tile; 2r=1.2*tile and (1.2*2.2)*tile are nobler than (2*2)*w and (2r=1.2)*wooden; (2*2)*tile is steadier. On the other hand, walk on the wooden floor or wear larger heel bottom area of shoes (2*2cm) will feel more retro and younger; 1.2*2.2*t are more flighty. In the following section, we will have some discussions to speculate what these results mean, and why some data have significant differences and will form principles for designers' references.

Table 1. Compare the scores between female and male.

	Modern —Retro	Casual —Formal	Temperament —Vulgar	Young —Old	Noble —Poor	Steady —Flighty
(2*2)*t	0.9831	0.0012 *	0.4542	0.1410	0.2223	0.1363
(1.2*2.2)*t	0.9099	0.3053	0.1997	0.8085	0.8422	0.3474
(2r=1.2)*t	0.7771	0.6427	0.2003	0.0168 *	0.3759	0.1880
(2*2)*w	0.1067	0.1607	0.6251	0.8325	0.0267 *	0.0270 *
(1.2*2.2)*t	0.8606	0.3463	0.0270 *	0.0777	0.0351 *	0.2688
(2r=1.2)*w	0.5051	0.3284	0.3261	0.6589	0.5083	0.6271

()=heel bottom area, w=wooden, t=tile

*Significant difference

Table 2. Mean material. (The higher score means the feeling is closer to the upper adjectives.)

	Modern —Retro	Casual —Formal	Temperament —Vulgar	Young —Old	Noble —Poor	Steady —Flighty
(2*2)*t	2.54	2.33	3.29	2.25	3.75	3.88
(1.2*2.2)*t	2.67	3.50	2.46	2.33	2.58	3.04
(2r=1.2)*t	4.42	3.58	3.50	3.83	3.33	2.58
(2*2)*w	2.21	2.96	2.54	2.04	2.96	3.71
(1.2*2.2)*t	4.21	3.13	3.71	3.75	3.79	3.08
(2r=1.2)*w	2.21	2.88	2.46	1.92	2.54	3.67

()=heel bottom area, w=wooden, t=tile

Table 3. Results of t-test on three pairs of the shoes.

Size(cm)	Modern —Retro	Casual —Formal	Temperament —Vulgar	Young —Old	Noble —Poor	Steady —Flighty
2r=1.2	1.0E-4 *	0.4294	0.0000 *	1.0E-4 *	0.0000 *	0.0602
1.2*2.2	1.0E-4 *	0.0514	0.0005 *	1.0E-4 *	0.2141	1.0E-4 *
2*2	0.6626	0.0000 *	0.0022 *	0.7724	0.0000 *	0.0141 *

*Significant difference

Table 4. Results of f-test on two materials of the floor.

	Modern —Retro	Casual —Formal	Temperament —Vulgar	Young —Old	Noble —Poor	Steady —Flighty
Tile	1.0E-4 *	0.0010 *	0.3527	1.0E-4 *	0.2705	0.0010 *
Wood	0.2040	0.0769	0.7288	0.3243	0.2669	0.0490 *

*Significant difference

Table 5. Results of Duncan tests on the variables of shoes at the heel bottom area.

Tasks	Grouping			
Modern	1.2*2.2cm	2r=1.2cm	2*2cm	Retro
Young	1.2*2.2cm	2r=1.2cm	2*2cm	Old

Table 6. Duncan tests on the heel bottom area and the material of the floor in all tasks in all tasks.

Tasks	Grouping						
Modern	(1.2*2.2)*t	(2r=1.2)*t	(2*2)*w	(2*2)*t	(2r=1.2)*w	(1.2*2.2)*w	Retro
Casual	(1.2*2.2)*t	(2*2)*w	(2r=1.2)*t	(1.2*2.2)*w	(2r=1.2)*w	(2*2)*t	Formal
Temperament	(2r=1.2)*t	(1.2*2.2)*t	(2*2)*t	(1.2*2.2)*w	(2r=1.2)*w	(2*2)*w	Vulgar
Young	(1.2*2.2)*t	(2r=1.2)*t	(2*2)*w	(2*2)*t	(1.2*2.2)*w	(2r=1.2)*w	Old
Noble	(2r=1.2)*t	(1.2*2.2)*t	(2*2)*t	(1.2*2.2)*w	(2*2)*w	(2r=1.2)*w	Poor
Steady	(2*2)*t	(1.2*2.2)*w	(2r=1.2)*w	(2r=1.2)*t	(2*2)*w	(1.2*2.2)*t	Flighty

()=heel bottom area, w=wooden, t=tile

3. Discussion

As shown in table 1, it shows that males and females have similar feeling under most conditions. But the different items do not have a consistency change, so in the following we will have some speculations about why they are different. After the experiment, we have an interview with the participants. The participants said that it's difficult to score the sound because it's not like in a visual test where they have a clear standard to grade the scores. So participants graded by what images they have when they hear the sound. We can see the differences

between males and females in this kind of transformation. When female participants hear the sounds, they will think what kind of the heeled shoes they are or what they may look like. However, even if the male participants know these are the shoes' sounds, they cannot imagine the shoes image in their mind. Instead, they claim to have associated the sounds with other things, such as drums, stakes, doors and so on. It may be a reason why males and females have different scores in some cases. Also, even though all females imagine the shoes, their imaginations may be different by their experience, culture, and subjective individual.

In table 2 and table 3, the data show “modern—retro” may have some relationships with “young—old”. By comparing the sound samples, it seems that if the sounds sound brighter, people will feel younger and more modern. And we also know that three pairs of the shoes have significant differences in the “temperament—vulgar” pair and the scores are higher (more temperament) when the shoes walking on the tile floor. An overview of the data suggests that people will have different feelings with different floor materials.

Except for the adjective pair “steady-flighty”, none of the others have a significant difference in wooden floor, as shown in table 4. But the p value of the adjectives pair “steady-flighty” is 0.049, just a little bit smaller than 0.05. So we could said, when the shoes are walking on the wooden floor, most people cannot tell the differences between these three pairs of the shoes. Back to the original average in table 2, as a whole, we can find out that people feel more retro, more formal, more vulgar, older, poorer, and steadier when they hear the sounds of shoes walking on wooden floor. It may be because when shoes are walking on the wooden floor, it has some echo and the sounds will be lower than walking on the tile floor. That is, floor material plays a critical role in auditory kansei of shoes' sound.

In table 5 and table 6, the data pointed out that the smaller the bottom area, (1.2×2.2) *tile and $(2r=1.2)$ *tile, the more modern and younger the feel is; (1.2×2.2) *tile is the most casual; (2×2) *tile is the steadier form. But the designer can only control the heel size of the shoes, so if we have to give the designer some principles, we should look at table 5. The combination (1.2×2.2) *tile and $(2r=1.2)$ *tile are more modern and younger.

The results differ from some of the predictions. In my opinion, the thinner the heel(the smaller the heel bottom area), the crisper the sounds. And crisp sounds gives a more modern, more casual, more temperament, nobler, and younger feel. The material of floors will have some but not much impact. In fact, the result shows that the material of the floor really has significantly influence to the sound. Outcome shows some feelings are more relevant to the material of floor, such as temperament and noble.

After the experiment the participants have some suggestions. Some people said that some adjectives are more related to the sounds' tempo rather than the timbre. So they had difficulty to give the score. Second, they want to give the samples relative scores by comparing sounds at the same time but not absolute scores as we asked them to do in the experiment. Also someone suggests that the sample should have diminuendo that make the sounds more natural.

4. Conclusion

We could conclude some key points based on the above outcome discussions and give some advice to the designer of the shoes:

- People tend to transform the sound into an image in their mind to give the score. So different culture,

background may have different feelings. Designer must get to know their target consumers.

- The adjectives “modern—retro” may have some relationships with “young—old”. If the designer want to design the shoes which make people feel modern and young, the bottom area should be smaller ($2r=1.2\text{cm}$ or $1.2*2.2\text{cm}$).

From this experiment, we can provide some suggestions for the future related tests:

- In the beginning of the experiments, allow participants to listen to all sound samples so that they can have an overall idea about all the sounds. Then broadcast the sound samples again to ask them to give the score to each sample.
- The score should not be an absolute number (such as 1 or 3). The better method to grade the score is to ask participants to draw a mark on a line which has the number 0 and 5 at the two ends. It would be better if participants can use relative comparisons between samples to give the scores.
- It might be helpful to use the method of interview or think aloud to know why participants have these feeling after the quantitative research. Maybe qualitative research will be clearer than quantitative research in order to know the reason of what characteristics of the sound will produce certain feelings.

We want to understand the relationship between sound and the characteristics of the heel by this thesis. Thus to give some design principles to the designer. But only three kinds of heel bottom areas of shoes are included in this paper. So this study is more like a pilot experiment. If experiments can include all heel sizes of the shoes in the future, the result may be more relevant and provides clearer design principles for designer. And then we can do more experiments to make sure if the principles can be expanded and if they are appropriate for all products. Designer may not only consider the appearance (visual) and material (touch), but also the sounds (auditory) in the future.

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